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Managing Teaching Staff For Service Delivery In Public Secondary Schools In Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the strategies for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Two (2) research questions and 2 hypotheses were answered and tested in the study, respectively. The design of the study was an analytic descriptive survey with the population as the 164 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. These schools have 164, from which 115 (70%) were selected as a sample, using the stratified sampling technique. Respondents responded to a validated instrument titled Managing Teaching Staff for Service Delivery in Public Secondary Schools Questionnaire (MTSSDPSSQ) designed by the researcher after the modified 4-point Likert scale model, with a reliability index of 0.76, obtained using test-retest. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while the z-test was used in testing the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. From the findings so far, it is crystal clear that for teaching staff in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State to offer quality service delivery, there is a need for proper management for the desired outcome to take effect. It was found out in the study that adequate remuneration encourages teachers' commitment to work and also increases teachers' performance. It was recommended that the institutions, in collaboration with the government, should establish a functional framework to enable teaching staff to undergo training that is required by making funds readily available for supervision of these programmes in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Keywords: management, teaching staff, service delivery, remuneration, in-service training programmes, public secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

Education is widely regarded as a productive endeavour with specific objectives and inputs, which include both human and material resources. The success of education largely depends on the quality of the teaching staff and their effectiveness in fulfilling their responsibilities. Therefore, any nation that aims to achieve the goals of its educational system must recognise the importance of staffing and create an environment conducive to teaching and learning for the delivery of quality education. In Nigeria, it has long been acknowledged that without qualified teachers, the educational objectives outlined in the National Policy on Education cannot be realised. Although the government may establish new schools and implement changes to the structure and curriculum, as well as recommend teaching methods and aids, ultimately, it is the teachers who are responsible for executing these directives. Teachers play a crucial role in translating educational objectives into knowledge and skills, which they then impart to students in the classroom. To facilitate this process, teachers must establish a classroom environment characterised by orderliness, discipline, and control. They must also be able to diagnose students' feelings and attitudes

based on their behaviour and responses. Achieving these goals is challenging without effective management of teaching staff, which includes providing essential support such as fair remuneration (including housing, transportation, and health allowances), in-service training programs (such as seminars, conferences, and workshops), and a conducive working environment with adequate teaching resources.

The remuneration package should not only consist of salaries or wages but also encompass additional benefits like accommodation, health coverage, transportation, communication allowances, and food assistance. A well-structured remuneration package can help attract and retain qualified teachers while fostering a positive attitude toward their work. Moreover, the remuneration should reflect the job requirements and be commensurate with the responsibilities of the position, as well as the skills and abilities of the employee. When remuneration is mismanaged or not provided promptly, employees may seek alternative means to meet their needs, diverting their attention and negatively impacting the quality of service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

To enhance the service delivery of teaching staff in secondary schools, teachers need to participate in in-service training programs such as seminars, conferences, and workshops. These programs help update teachers on current trends in the education sector and support their personal development, ultimately boosting their interest and contributing to better service delivery. Azikiwe (2008) emphasised that in-service education programs are vital for informing teachers about new developments, teaching techniques, and organizational procedures. These may include approaches such as the conceptual approach, inquiry-based teaching, simulation, role-playing, systems thinking, open-plan classrooms, and the use of a wide range of audio materials. In-service education plays a crucial role in meeting the challenges of our time, given the rapid growth of knowledge alongside technological, social, and cultural advancements.

The work environment significantly influences the quality of service delivery. Therefore, classrooms should be well-managed, providing a comfortable atmosphere with air conditioning or fans, proper lighting, and comfortable seating for both teachers and students. Management should ensure that teachers are actively involved in key decision-making processes, fostering a sense of belonging. Additionally, secondary education serves as the educational stage between primary and higher education. It is the second tier of education that prepares students for their political and economic roles in society. Secondary education is defined as the education children receive after completing primary education and before pursuing higher education.

The broad aims of secondary education within Nigeria's overall national objectives are to prepare students for useful living in society and higher education. The government plans for secondary education to last six years, divided into two stages: junior secondary school and senior secondary school, each lasting three years. The junior secondary school offers both pre-vocational and academic education and is tuition-free. The senior secondary school is for students who are capable and willing to engage in a more comprehensive six-year secondary education. It features a core curriculum designed to broaden students' knowledge and perspectives.

The core subjects that all students must take, in addition to their chosen specialties, include English Language, Mathematics, one Nigerian Language, one of the following subjects: Physics, Chemistry, or Biology, and one literature subject from English, History, or Geography, along with Agricultural Science or another vocational subject. The primary aims of this education system focus on preparing students for meaningful participation in society and for pursuing higher education. Additionally, the system fosters respect for diverse viewpoints, the dignity of labour, and an appreciation for the values outlined in the broad national aims. According to the National Policy on Education (2004), the general goals of secondary education are to:

1. Provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for higher education, regardless of sex, social status, religion, or background.
2. Offer a diversified curriculum that caters to different talents, opportunities, and future roles.
3. Provide trained manpower in applied sciences, technology, and commerce at sub-professional levels.

4. Develop and promote Nigerian languages, arts, and culture within the context of global cultural heritage.

To achieve these objectives, it is essential to equip the workforce (teachers) through ongoing retraining to align them with these goals. Unfortunately, there is often a misplacement of priorities among administrators, who fail to adequately manage and attend to the welfare of teaching staff. This neglect can demotivate teachers, undermining their ability to deliver quality education. Moreover, the principal plays a crucial role as the head of administration in secondary school education. It is their responsibility to ensure quality management of facilities, personnel, and information to achieve effective job delivery. According to Nwogu (2005), while industries produce goods and services, the education sector transforms illiterate citizens into educated individuals. To maximise teachers' productivity, there must be a conducive relationship between their work environment, job design, and the availability of infrastructural facilities. Additionally, safe and healthy working conditions, opportunities for social interaction, recognition, advancement, growth, and job security are essential. Poor management of teaching staff can lead to inadequate handling of other institutional resources, such as finance, equipment, and time.

In summary, school administrators need to be aware of the evolving needs of teaching staff and provide flexible working conditions to maintain their morale, commitment, and job satisfaction, thus reducing stress and challenges at work.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers around the world face the challenge of balancing their professional responsibilities with personal needs due to the long hours they dedicate to meeting and often exceeding organisational expectations to secure their jobs. Many educators believe that inadequate pay, limited in-service training, subpar facilities, and poor working conditions have negatively affected both their mental health and overall happiness. However, high productivity in secondary education is largely dependent on the effectiveness of the teaching staff. The performance of teachers, in turn, hinges on how well their work environment supports their personal needs.

Despite this, governments often argue that significant progress has been made in managing the quality of work life for teachers through improved salary packages and other benefits, without recognizing a corresponding increase in the educational system's productivity. Moreover, critics point to the teaching staff as a source of poor quality in education, citing a lack of innovative research initiatives and limited impact of secondary school activities on community development as evidence of inadequate performance. This raises concerns that warrant further investigation. Teachers around the world face the challenge of balancing their professional responsibilities with personal needs due to the long hours they dedicate to meeting and often exceeding organisational expectations to secure their jobs. Many educators believe that inadequate pay, limited in-service training, subpar facilities, and poor working conditions have negatively affected both their mental health and overall happiness. However, high productivity in secondary education is largely dependent on the effectiveness of the teaching staff. The performance of teachers, in turn, hinges on how well their work environment supports their personal needs.

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Aim and Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the strategies for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The specific objectives of this study include:

1. Find out how adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

2. Determine how in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

1. In what ways provision of adequate remuneration be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
2. In what ways can in-service training programmes be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided this study:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on how the provision of adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on how in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Significance of the Study

The results of this study will be of benefit to the education system in the following ways: It will sensitise school administrators on the components of teaching, staff management and properly direct them on what to package for their staff to enhance productivity in the education system. It will motivate the Bayelsa State Government through its education service to recall that managing teaching staff contributes to the quality of education delivery in public secondary schools. It will also enhance teachers' personal and organisational skills, abilities and knowledge for effective and efficient performance since provisions of infrastructure, facilities, and equipment will be doggedly pursued in the state. The result of this work will also serve as a primary source of material for researchers or those who may wish to carry out further research on this topic or other related topics.

Literature Reviews

Quality Education Delivery

Education service delivery refers to the level of competence and performance of workers in achieving the established goals and objectives. The outcomes of educational programs typically result in employees entering the workforce in various settings. This means that service delivery has a significant impact not only on the school system but also on society as a whole. According to Koko, Blessing, Oba, and Bassey (2007), education service delivery ensures that all necessary precautions have been taken to produce results that meet the needs, expectations, and satisfaction of consumers. The rationale behind the quality of education lies in the necessity to align educational programs with individual manpower requirements. As graduates of educational programs transition into the workforce, the quality of education has a ripple effect that influences both the school system and the nation. The future of society heavily relies on the quality of its current educational system.

Okeke (2001), in an inaugural lecture, defined the quality of educational services as being tied to significant purpose, productivity, academic excellence, and effectiveness. Effective service delivery empowers teachers and administrators to enhance the educational system, ensuring that classroom practices and management operate at the highest possible standards. Moreover, teaching methods and management strategies must remain current and relevant within the global community.

Provision of adequate remuneration as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery.

Remuneration is a key aspect of teachers' work conditions that significantly impacts their job performance. Teachers, managers, and administrators are more likely to be motivated to work effectively if they are well-compensated for their services, which in turn enhances the quality of work in the educational system. Nakpodia (2006) suggested that job security in terms of income and employment stability promotes long-term commitment among personnel. Conversely, when teachers' salaries are not

paid on time, their level of commitment tends to decline. Frequent industrial actions due to the non-payment of teachers' salaries, leave, remuneration, and other allowances are common among secondary school teachers. As a result, many teachers are compelled to pursue other business opportunities, leading to teaching becoming a secondary occupation rather than their primary focus. Furthermore, a lack of adequate motivation within the system has detrimental effects on staff performance. According to Olubusayo, Stephen, and Maxwell (2014), the success and sustainability of any educational institution hinge on how employees are compensated and rewarded. A well-structured reward system and motivating incentives can enhance employee commitment and ultimately increase productivity within educational institutions.

Motivation serves as a driving force within the organisation, encouraging workers to contribute positively to its progress. Human beings generally require a combination of internal and external drivers, incentives, encouragement, and the satisfaction of basic needs to perform at their best and achieve group goals. The quality of teachers, as well as that of other supporting staff, along with their level of motivation and work environment, can significantly influence the overall atmosphere of the school and the performance of the students. Promotions, discipline, transfers, and periodic evaluations of secondary school teachers should aim to improve their performance and productivity. School managers must adapt their attitudes and performance to foster productivity and equality in education. Igani (2005) identified five essential components of working conditions necessary for teachers' effectiveness: salary, fringe benefits, responsibilities, rights, and obligations. Given the workload of the average Nigerian teacher and their vital role in nation-building, they should regularly receive bonuses, allowances, and other fringe benefits to maintain their happiness and productivity on the job.

Unfortunately, teachers in Bayelsa State often do not receive these essential allowances for housing, transportation, healthcare, children's education, bonuses, or other forms of fringe benefits. Edem (2006) argued that for teaching to be recognised and valued, the average annual income for teachers, along with adequate provisions for advancement, promotion, and benefits enjoyed by those in other professions, must be ensured. In summary, to enable teachers to be productive and perform their duties to the best of their ability, their welfare must be prioritised.

In-service training programmes as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery.

In-service training is a human resource development program designed to enhance the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of an organisation's employees. Study leave may be granted with or without pay. Study leave with pay allows the beneficiary to receive their basic salary while attending school, but they do not receive other entitlements. In contrast, study leave without pay means that employees are not entitled to any salary or supportive allowances. Ehirim (2010) defines in-service education as all activities undertaken by professional personnel during their employment, aimed at improving their job performance. Azikiwe (2008) asserts that in-service education programs are necessary to inform teachers about new developments, teaching techniques, and organisational procedures, including conceptual approaches, inquiry teaching, simulations, role-playing, system approaches, open-plan environments, and the use of various audio materials.

In-service education plays a crucial role in meeting the challenges presented by the rapid growth of knowledge, as well as technological, social, and cultural changes. Clolfolter (2005) identifies several key goals of in-service education, including the continuous improvement of teachers' performance, effectiveness, and efficiency in classroom-related activities. He emphasises that teachers must enhance their performance to meet the accountability pressures associated with being exposed to new ideas and techniques through in-service education. According to the Department of Education (1998), in-service training (INSET) should be viewed as an ongoing process of professional development. In-service education programs aim to address the deficiencies of school teachers, allowing the collective effort of all staff members to contribute to the efficiency of the Nigerian educational system, provided that teachers' needs align with the system's requirements.

In-service education and training is a process through which teachers continually enhance their skills, knowledge, and attitudes while remaining employed. This approach aims to correct deficiencies in teaching staff and promote professional growth. Ukeje (2007) notes that in-service education fosters professional development, helping to alleviate existing gaps in ideas, skills, and methods. He further suggests that comprehensive human resource development should extend beyond merely maintaining teaching staff standards through in-service education. Opportunities should be created for educators to enhance their quality by acquiring new skills and knowledge. It is important to note that study leave and in-service training are interrelated, though there are subtle differences between the two.

On-the-Job Training: This is a method whereby a trainee learns on the job. Igwe (1992) views on-the-job training as those professional development programmes in which one engages after initial certification. Davar (2003), however, explains that on-the-job training is a type of education that can only be secured through experience.

Workshops/Conferences/Seminars: These are well-established human resource development programmes. Nnabuo (2001) notes that a well-trained (teaching) staff requires courses such as workshops, conferences and seminars to update their knowledge and skills to meet contemporary demands of the job. They entail presentation of quality papers by experts on general and topical educational issues, with a view to proffering solutions that will bring about uniformity and stability in the education industry.

Mamoria and Gankar (2008) define a conference as a formal meeting organised to promote knowledge and understanding through significant oral participation from attendees. Conferences prioritise small group discussions, structured subject matter, and active participation, allowing conferees to contribute meaningfully to the body of knowledge. In contrast, workshops typically involve experts lecturing with limited input from attendees, while seminars focus on paper presentations by one or more individuals on topics selected in consultation with the seminar organisers.

Ademalekun (1989), cited in Mmerem (2014), notes that seminars and workshops are short-duration activities designed for more experienced teaching staff. They encourage discussions centred on specific problems or topical issues, broadening participants' perspectives and enhancing their knowledge and experience in the subject matter. Human resource development programs are essential for teaching staff to ensure they are effective and efficient in their roles. These programs not only enhance the intellectual capital of educators but also positively impact student performance in tertiary institutions, contributing to the development of a robust and equitable society. Ajayi (2005) defines capacity building as the process through which individuals, organisations, and societies develop the necessary abilities to perform functions, solve problems, and set and achieve goals. Okorie, as cited in Nwideduh (2003), emphasises the importance of teacher development in education, stating that it is essential for the continual renewal, upgrading, and updating of teachers' knowledge and skills through capacity-building programs. Such programs equip teachers with the skills necessary to build and maintain positive relationships with staff and to motivate students for optimal results.

Research shows that students taught by teachers without professional preparation tend to learn less and perform below average compared to those taught by professionally trained educators. According to Okorie (2009), despite an employee's pre-service training, ongoing renewal, upgrading, and updating of knowledge, skills, and capabilities are necessary to keep pace with our rapidly changing society, particularly in light of advancements in science and technology. Educational institutions must implement well-defined staff development policies to achieve better outcomes; otherwise, they may face challenges related to organisational stagnation. In this context, quality pertains to how well the learning opportunities available to students enable them to attain their educational goals. It involves ensuring that appropriate and effective teaching supports assessment and provides valuable learning opportunities. The work environment is a critical strategy for managing teaching staff and delivering services effectively. Academic staff performance is influenced by various factors, one of which is the school environment. This includes infrastructural facilities such as school buildings, staff offices, laboratories, libraries, and

recreational facilities for both staff and students. Ensuring that these elements are in good condition can positively influence teachers' attitudes towards their work.

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for the study was the analytic descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised the 164 public secondary schools and 164 principals in Bayelsa State. The sample of the study was 115 public secondary schools and their principal in the state. They were selected using the stratified sampling technique. Respondents' instrument titled: 'Managing Teaching Staff for Service Delivery in Public Secondary Schools Questionnaire (MTSSDPSSQ). The instrument was designed by the researcher in the modified 4-point Likert Scale model. To ensure face and content validity of the instrument, the researcher submitted it to two experts who scrutinised and moderated the instrument. To establish the reliability coefficient of the instrument, a test-retest method was used to obtain the reliability. 20 sets of the instrument were administered to 20 principals who did not form a part of the sample of the study, and their responses were retrieved for coding and subjected to statistical analysis using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient method, and a reliability index of 0.76 was obtained. The instrument of the study was self-administered to the respondents in their schools by the researcher, with assistance from 2 research assistants who were properly educated on their expected roles. In all, 115 copies of the instrument were distributed, while 111 (99%) were retrieved. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while – test was used in testing the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What ways provision of adequate remuneration be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Mean of Male and Female Science Teachers on the ways provision of adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

S/No	Items	Male principals n=68		Female principals n=43		Mean Set	
		Mean \bar{X}_1	SD	Mean \bar{X}_2	SD	X \bar{X}	Decision
1	The security of workers in terms of income and employment.	3.05	1.24	3.06	1.25	3.06	Agreed
2	When teachers' salaries are paid as due	3.68	1.62	3.47	1.48	3.53	Agreed
3	Giving housing allowance to save staff from extra cost, this will create the right psychology to perform better.	2.63	1.12	3.10	1.27	2.87	Agreed
4	Provision of health care bonuses enhances the teaching staff's performance	3.41	1.44	3.37	1.42	3.39	Agreed
5	Study leave for regular programme with pay gives a sense of belongingness, which enhances their performance.	2.63	1.13	3.10	1.27	2.87	Agreed

6	Provision of incentives like transportation to teaching staff encourages them to be more active in discharging their duties	3.30	1.38	3.70	1.64	2.97	Agreed
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		3.06		3.30	0.92	3.12	Agreed

Data in Table 1 indicate that item 2 had the highest mean score of 3.58, followed by item 4 with 3.39, item 1 with 3.06, item 6 with 2.97, and items 3 and 5 with 2.87. The various scores were above the criterion mean of 2.50 for agreeing or disagreeing with the items of the questionnaire. With the result, it indicated that the ways provision of adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State when there is security of workers in term of income and employment, when teacher's salaries are paid as at when due, giving housing allowance to save staff from extra cost, this will create in the right psychology to perform better, provision of health care bonuses enhance teaching staffs performance, study leave for regular programme with pay gives sense of belongingness which enhances their performance and provision of incentives like transportation to teaching staffs encourages them to be more active in discharging their duties.

Research Question Two: What ways can in-service training programmes be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings on the ways in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

S/No	Items	Male n=68 Mean \bar{X}_1	principals SD	Female n=43 Mean \bar{X}_2	Principals SD	Mean Set \bar{X}	Decision
7	Keeping teaching staff up to standard through the acquisition of new skills and knowledge	3.40	1.43	3.27	1.36	3.34	Agreed
8	Attending seminar programmes often contributes to teaching staff productivity	3.50	1.50	3.30	1.38	3.40	Agreed
9	Professional higher education qualification programmes like sandwich programmes will give teaching staff a sense of promotion, which triggers their interest in the job	2.90	1.19	2.80	1.16	2.85	Agreed
10	Orientation induction workshop for new teachers encourages them to be active in service	3.01	1.23	3.19	1.31	3.10	Agreed

	Collaborative research work enhances their knowledge in the teaching and learning process	3.19	1.31	3.10	1.27	3.15	Agreed
11	The experiences acquired through conferences attended by teaching staff boost their level of productivity in school	2.80	1.14	2.89	1.18	2.85	Agreed
12	The knowledge acquired through workshops enhances teaching staff performance.	3.20	1.32	3.02	1.23	3.11	Agreed
	Grand Mean and Standard Deviation	3.14		3.08		3.11	Agreed

Data in Table 1 indicate that item 8 had the highest mean score of 3.40, followed by item 7 with 3.34, item 6 with 3.34, item 11 with 3.15, item 9 with 3.11, item 10 with 3.10 3 and item 6 with 2.85, respectively. The various scores were above the criterion mean of 2.50 for agreeing or disagreeing with the items of the questionnaire. With the result, it simply imply that the ways in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State is by keeping teaching staffs up to standard through the acquisition of new skills and knowledge, attending seminar programmes often contribute to teaching staff productivity, professional higher education qualification programmes like sandwich programmes will give teaching staffs a sense of promotion which triggers their interest on the job, orientation induction workshop for new teachers encourages them to be active in service, collaborative research work enhances their knowledge in the teaching and learning process, the experiences acquired through conferences attended by teaching staffs boost their level of productivity in school, and the knowledge acquired through workshops enhance teaching staff performance.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on how the provision of adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Ratings of Male and Female Science Teachers on how provision of adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	Z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male principals	68	3.06	1.33	2				
				109	-0.90	1.96	0.05	Not Accepted
Female principals	43	3.30	1.13					
Total	111			111				

Data in Table 3 shows the value of z-cal. To be -0.90 while the value of z-crit. was +-1.96. Since the value of z-cal. Of -0.90 is greater than the values of z-crit. Of 1.96 at 109 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not accepted, and this implied that there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on how the provision of

adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on how in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Summary of Z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Ratings of Male and Female Science Teachers on how in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	Z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male Science Teachers	68	3.14	1.30	2 109	-0.24	+1.96	0.05	Not Accepted
Female Science Teachers	43	3.08	1.27					

Data on Table 4, shows the value of z-cal. Of -0.24 was more than the value of z-crit. of -1.96 and as such, the null hypothesis was not accepted and this implied that there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on how in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS/IMPLICATIONS

Managing Physical Hazards for Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

The first finding of the study is that the ways in-service training programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State is by keeping teaching staffs up to standard through the acquisition of new skills and knowledge, attending seminar programmes often contribute to teaching staff productivity, professional higher education qualification programmes like sandwich programmes will give teaching staffs a sense of promotion which triggers their interest on the job, orientation induction workshop for new teachers encourages them to be active in service, collaborative research work enhances their knowledge in the teaching and learning process, the experiences acquired through conferences attended by teaching staffs boost their level of productivity in school, and the knowledge acquired through workshops enhance teaching staff performance. Also, a corresponding finding from a test of hypothesis establishes a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female principals on how the provision of adequate remuneration can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The findings align with the studies conducted by Nnahuo (2001), who found that a well-trained (teaching) staff requires courses such as workshops, conferences and seminars to update their knowledge and skills to meet contemporary demands of the job. They entail presentation of quality papers by experts on general and topical educational issues, with a view to proffering solutions that will bring about uniformity and stability in the education industry.

Managing Environmental Hazards for a Sustainable Learning Environment in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

The second findings of the study showed ways for managing environmental hazards for a sustainable learning environment are the Maintenance of waste disposal or dump sites to prevent environmental hazards, access to portable water, Provision of surveillance equipment makes it easy to ensure healthy school usage. While Access to clean water makes for environmental cleanliness in schools, and provision of surveillance equipment was disagreed upon. Also, a corresponding finding from a test of hypothesis established a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female principals on how in-service training

programmes can be used as a strategy for managing teaching staff for service delivery in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. These findings align with the studies conducted by Nakpodia.

CONCLUSIONS

From the findings so far, it is crystal clear that for teaching staff in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State to offer quality service delivery, there is a need for proper management for the desired outcome to take effect. It was found out in the study that adequate remuneration encourages teachers' commitment to work and also increases teachers' performance. It was recommended that the institutions, in collaboration with the government, should establish a functional framework to enable teaching staff to undergo training that is required by making funds readily available for supervision of these programmes in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

1. It was recommended that the institutions, in collaboration with the government, should establish a functional framework to enable teaching staff to undergo training that is required by making funds readily available for supervision of these programmes in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
2. Government should implement special intervention to improve teaching and learning in all public schools by providing adequate and functional facilities, improving condition of service for teachers and also improve the general climate of the school system.

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